

A Thousand Years of Two Italian Families: The “de Judicibus” and “Giliberti” Digital Genealogical Archive

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Abstract

This paper describes a large-scale digital genealogical archive documenting two Italian family lineages — *de Judicibus* and *Giliberti* — across a span of approximately one thousand years, from the tenth to the twenty-first century. The archive, accessible as a website developed entirely by the author, as of June 2026, contains records of about 4,100 individuals distributed across Italy and fifteen other countries, drawn from primary sources including Latin notarial acts, diocesan registers, cadastral archives, heraldic documents, and personal manuscripts. The paper discusses the structure of the resource, the methodological criteria adopted for source evaluation and genealogical attribution, the technical architecture of the platform, and the research questions the archive makes tractable. The resource is offered as a freely accessible reference tool for historians, genealogists, and researchers working on medieval and early modern Italian social history.

1. Introduction

Genealogical databases have become an established category of digital humanities resources, ranging from large commercial platforms to focused scholarly archives. Most such resources, however, aggregate data across many families with limited depth per lineage, or conversely concentrate on a single generation within a well-documented noble house. Sustained multi-century documentation of two related but distinct family lines, integrating primary archival sources, onomastic analysis, genetic data, and a purpose-built digital infrastructure, remains comparatively rare, particularly for families of mixed social standing.

The archive presented here covers the *de Judicibus* and *Giliberti* families from their earliest documented attestations — the tenth century for the former, the eleventh for the latter — to living generations. Research began in the early 1980s, conducted independently by Filippo Giliberti (1902–1995) and Danilo de Judicibus (1930–2019), and was subsequently unified and expanded by the present author, who also designed and built the digital platform from scratch. The current version of the archive (v14.8.0, June 2026) corresponds to a generated PDF of more than 5,400 pages, though the online resource is considerably richer in interactive features.

The archive is periodically converted into this PDF format and uploaded to ResearchGate as a citable resource. The most recent available version (December 2025) is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13779.23842>.

The two families intersect at a single documented marriage: Danilo de Judicibus and Maria Teresa Giliberti, married in 1956, making the author a direct descendant of both lines. This personal stake in the research does not diminish its scholarly scope; on the contrary, it has sustained four decades of archival work across Italian regions and abroad.

2. The Two Family Lines

2.1 The de Judicibus family

The surname *de Judicibus* derives from the Latin *iudex* (plural *iudices*), which in the early medieval period denoted not a judicial magistrate but a local administrative or governing role. The earliest documented bearers of the name appear in the tenth century in two geographically separate areas: the region around Isola Comacina on Lake Como, which was at the time a Byzantine enclave, and the town of Ventimiglia in Liguria, also among the last territories in the region to remain under Byzantine control. Whether these two early clusters represent branches of a single family or distinct lineages sharing a common occupational surname is a question the research has not yet been able to resolve.

From Ventimiglia, the family expanded along the Ligurian coast to Genoa and subsequently to Naples, Sicily, and — from the fifteenth century — to Apulia, particularly Molfetta, from which the author's direct paternal line descends. Parallel branches are documented in Valtellina, the Varese area, Dalmatia (Split), Portugal, France (Limoges, Nice, the Maritime Alps), and, from the nineteenth century onward, in Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Chile, Uruguay, and the United States.

The surname presents numerous orthographic variants across the centuries — *Iudex*, *Iudicis*, *de Iudicibus*, *Del Giudice*, *Giudici*, *De' Giudici* — reflecting both the grammatical declension practices of Latin notarial language and the progressive replacement of Latin by Italian in official documents. Modern variants include forms distorted by immigration officials, particularly in the United States and South America.

Notable individuals documented in the archive include Ottone Iudicis, who participated in the Crusades; Martino de Judicibus, documented as a crew member on Magellan and Elcano's circumnavigation of the globe (1519–1522); and Giovanni Battista de Judicibus de Finaria, tutor to Giuliano della Rovere, later Pope Julius II.

2.2 The Giliberti family

The surname *Giliberti* derives from Gilbert Quarrel Drengot, a Norman knight of the eleventh century and son of Roberto Drengot, whose family was among the first Norman lineages to settle in southern Italy. The name entered Italian usage as a patronymic — *Giliberto* — and stabilised in its current plural form by the seventeenth century. The family is listed among the noble families of Solofra (Avellino) in the sixteenth-century *Historia della Città e del Regno di Napoli* by Summonte.

The primary branch originates in Solofra, from which descend the Celenza and Carlantino branch, the Saponara branch, and the Sant'Arsenio branch, among others. The family subsequently spread across much of southern Italy and, through emigration, to the Americas, North Africa (Tunisia, Algeria), and Australia. Unlike the de Judicibus lineage, the Giliberti surname shows minimal orthographic variation, though immigration records occasionally introduce distortions.

Among the notable individuals documented in the Giliberti archive is Francesco Saverio Giliberto (Solofra, 1551 – Montevergine, 1607), who served as Abbot General of the Congregation of Montevergine from 17 May 1599 until his death in 1607. His abbacy coincided with a critical phase of the Counter-Reformation reform of the Congregation, promoted under Clement VIII through the apostolic commissioner Giovanni Leonardi. Over eight years of

governance, Giliberto oversaw the consolidation of monastic discipline, the reorganisation of novitiate education, the suppression of non-observant houses, and the resolution of jurisdictional disputes with neighbouring dioceses. His administration was later assessed by historians of the Congregation as one of the most effective in establishing lasting observance of the Benedictine reform within the Verginiano order.

The second figure of particular scholarly interest is Onofrio Giliberti (Solofra, c. 1616–1618 – c. 1664–1666), dramatist, mathematician, and astronomer. He is best known for his «Il Convitato di Pietra» (Naples, Francesco Savio, 1653), today lost, which represents the first appearance of the Don Juan figure in Italian drama, drawing on Tirso de Molina’s *El burlador de Sevilla* (1630) and predating Molière’s *Dom Juan* (1665). The French scholar G. Gendarme de Bévotte, in his 1907 critical edition of the pre-Molière Don Juan sources, identified in Giliberti’s text an original dramatic element — the pilgrim figure — absent from all earlier versions and not traceable to any known source. Onofrio also published a treatise on astronomy, «Le Ruote dell’Universo» (Naples, Savio, 1646), and is recorded as having predicted the apparition of Halley’s Comet of 20 December 1664. His dramatic output, which includes sacred plays and comedies as well as secular dramas, was dedicated almost exclusively to the Orsini princes of Solofra, one of whom, Pietro Francesco Orsini, later became Pope Benedict XIII (1724).

3. Scope and Content of the Archive

The archive currently documents 4,089 individuals across both family lines, organised into branches (*rami*) defined primarily by geographic area of stable settlement. For the *de Judicibus* family, 24 branches are fully verified, covering 1,678 male and 681 female individuals; a further 11 branches are under ongoing investigation, adding 745 male and 273 female individuals. For the *Giliberti* family, 10 verified branches account for 454 male and 258 female individuals. The archive distinguishes three main clades for the *de Judicibus* — Tyrrhenian, Adriatic, and Alpine — while the *Giliberti* documentation is organised around a primary southern Italian clade centred on Campania.

Each individual entry, where sources permit, includes dates and places of birth, marriage, and death; references to the primary sources from which the information was drawn; notes on onomastic variants; and, for earlier periods, contextual historical commentary. Entries are linked to genealogical trees rendered as scalable vector graphics, to georeferenced maps of relevant localities, and, for selected branches, to transcriptions of original Latin documents.

The archive interface and all narrative content are in Italian. Primary source material is reproduced in the original language — medieval and modern Italian, medieval Latin, Croatian, French, Spanish, German, and English — with Italian translations provided in most cases. This reflects both the geographic spread of the two families and the diversity of the archival traditions from which the documentation is drawn. For non-Italian readers, the site includes a built-in page translation feature, defaulting to English, which provides access to the narrative content in other languages.

The archive also contains several thematically organised appendices: a full transcription of the relevant acts from the *Atti dell’Amandolesio* — a set of notarial acts from Ventimiglia drawn up by the notary Giovanni di Amandolesio (reconstructed from damaged parchments by palaeographer Laura Balletto) — selected for their bearing on the two family lines; a comprehensive history of Italy from the fifth to the nineteenth century provided as contextual reference; a chronological list of popes; a section on historical weights and measures used in

Italian archival documents; a register of ships involved in emigration; and a detailed gazetteer covering all localities mentioned in the archive, from Molfetta to Perth.

The Y-chromosome haplogroup analysis of the author is included as supplementary genetic data, situating the *de Judicibus* paternal line within the broader population genetics of the Italian peninsula.

4. Sources and Methodology

4.1 Source categories

The archive draws on three categories of sources, treated with explicit methodological distinctions.

Primary sources are documents produced by or directly contemporaneous with the individuals under study: notarial acts, diocesan registers, cadastral and land records, personal letters, inscriptions, and epigraphs. These are treated as the most reliable evidence for genealogical attribution.

Secondary sources are scholarly and historical works — monographs, published document editions, theses — that discuss or reproduce primary material, sometimes preserving records of documents since lost or destroyed. These are used with appropriate caution, given the risk of transcription errors and interpretive bias.

Oral tradition constitutes a third category, treated as a source of research hypotheses rather than established fact. Several family narratives passed down over generations have proven, on archival verification, to contain a substantial core of historical accuracy — including the Crusade participation and the circumnavigation — which has shaped the author's approach to oral material as a legitimate, if provisional, source of direction for archival enquiry.

4.2 Attribution criteria

Sharing a surname, even in the same locality, is not treated as sufficient evidence of family membership. Attribution relies on corroborating indicators: shared notaries, co-ownership of documented family properties, co-occurrence in the same documents alongside known family members, and consistency of heraldic evidence. The archive explicitly marks connections as verified (represented by solid lines in the genealogical maps) or unverified (dashed lines), and maintains a separate category for individuals who share the surname but whose connection to either family has not been established.

Onomastic complexity is a particular challenge for the *de Judicibus* line, given that *iudex* was also a functional title in medieval documents. The archive adopts the criterion that when the term appears in a list of personal names in the body of a notarial act — rather than in the subscription, where notaries and judges habitually signed — it is more likely to function as a surname.

4.3 Collaborative contributions

The archive incorporates contributions from twenty-one family members and fourteen external researchers, including university historians and archivists in Croatia (University of Zagreb, University of Split) who assisted with the documentation of the Dalmatian branch. All contributions have been verified against independent sources before inclusion.

5. Digital Architecture

The website was designed and built entirely by the author, using HTML5, CSS3, SVG2, PHP 8.1, JavaScript, jQuery, Bootstrap, and JSON as the underlying data format. Genealogical trees are generated dynamically from the JSON database using the BasicPrimitives library and rendered as interactive SVGs with pan and zoom functionality. Georeferenced maps are produced as vector graphics using Inkscape and integrated into the site. Historical photographs have been digitised and, where significantly degraded, restored using the GFP-GAN AI model.

The choice of JSON as the data format reflects a deliberate design decision: it allows the entire dataset to be queried, exported, and reused independently of the web interface, making the archive more durable and interoperable than a purely document-based system. The site is versioned — the current release is v14.8.0 — and a full PDF export of the content is generated automatically at each major release using the Prince typesetting engine.

With the exception of My Family Tree, a commercial application used to generate GEDCOM files for the genealogical trees, every component of the platform — from the data model to the user interface — was written from scratch by the author, who has a professional background in software development.

6. Research Applications

The archive supports several lines of enquiry that would be difficult or impossible to pursue without it.

For historians of medieval Liguria, the Amandolesio notarial acts provide a continuous documentary series covering the *de Judicibus* of Ventimiglia from the twelfth century, including property transactions, marriage contracts, and political affiliations during the Guelf-Ghibelline conflicts of the communal period.

For researchers working on Norman settlement in southern Italy, the *Giliberti* documentation provides detailed evidence of a family of Norman origin across nine centuries, from the Drengot lineage of the eleventh century to contemporary descendants in Campania and abroad.

For demographic and migration historians, the archive offers unusually detailed tracking of emigration patterns from specific Italian localities — Molfetta, Solofra, Ventimiglia — to Australia, the Americas, and North Africa across the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, including ship records and immigration documents.

For onomastic researchers, the archive provides a systematic record of surname variation in Latin and Italian documents from the twelfth to the twentieth century for two lineages with distinct morphological profiles.

The integration of Y-chromosome haplogroup data opens a further avenue for researchers interested in the intersection of genetic and documentary genealogy.

A substantial contribution to the research has come from the digitised archival material available through the “Portale degli Antenati” (<https://antenati.cultura.gov.it/>), the genealogical portal of the Italian Ministry of Culture, which provides open access to parish registers, civil records, and notarial documents from archives across Italy. The portal has proved an invaluable resource for the verification and expansion of numerous branches of both family lines, and merits recognition as one of the most significant digital heritage initiatives in Italian archival history.

7. Access and Ongoing Work

The archive is freely accessible at <https://genealogia.dejudicibus.it/>. No registration is required. The content is updated continuously as new documents are identified, digitised, or contributed by family members and collaborators.

Active research directions include the identification of a connecting link between the Ventimiglia and Apulian branches of the *de Judicibus* family; further investigation of the Byzantine hypothesis for the family's origins, based on the early association of both the Ventimiglia and Isola Comacina branches with territories that remained under Byzantine control until the late sixth century; and the expansion of the Dalmatian branch documentation through collaboration with Croatian university researchers.

A further open question concerns the connection between the Del Giudice family of Naples and Matteo de Judicibus, born in Campobasso (Molise) around 1703, who is the documented ancestor of all the modern Apulian branches of the de Judicibus and de Iudicibus lineages. Establishing this link would be a significant step toward a more complete reconstruction of the family's genealogical map in southern Italy.

The author acknowledges that a project of this scope and duration raises questions of long-term preservation. Steps to ensure continuity of the archive beyond the author's lifetime are under consideration.

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